

LAMINA WAVINESS LEVELS IN THICK COMPOSITES AND ITS EFFECT
ON THEIR COMPRESSION STRENGTH

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Abstract

Minor amounts of fiber undulation and misalignment are suspected to have a significant effect on the compression strength of composite materials. Theoretical analyses have shown that fibers that are misaligned only 2° from the principal load direction can reduce compression strength 60%. Little information is available regarding the amount of undulation and misalignment that actually is present in composite laminates.

In this investigation the lamina waviness at the specimen midplane was measured for 48 and 96 ply, [0₂/90]_S carbon/epoxy and S2 glass/epoxy laminates. Measurements were performed using an optical microscope equipped with an x-y vernier table. The data was compared with published data for unidirectional boron/epoxy composites. The composite samples investigated in this study were taken from panels fabricated for a study on the compression response of thick-section composites. A theoretical analysis was then conducted to determine the effect of the measured waviness on compression strength, and compression tests were conducted to verify the analysis.

The results showed the midplane wavelength-to-amplitude ratio to be comparable for the carbon, S2 glass, and boron composites and independent of specimen thickness. The only difference in characteristic waviness was seen between the longitudinal and transverse edges of the carbon reinforced laminates. In the transverse direction the stacking sequence was [90₂/0]_S, and midplane waviness was over twice that seen in the longitudinal or [0₂/90]_S direction.

The theoretical analysis and experimental results correlated well and showed that fiber misalignment associated with initial waviness and subsequent

compression loading accounted for decreasing compression strength with increasing specimen thickness.

KEYWORDS: Composites, compression failure, fiber waviness, thick composites,

1. Introduction

Fiber curvature and misalignment have been theoretically shown to have a significant effect on the compression response of composite materials (1-7), however very little work has been done to quantify the amount of this curvature or misalignment in actual composite coupons. Davis (1) has quantified the fiber curvature present in unidirectional boron/epoxy coupons, and Yurgartis (8) has measured and statistically analyzed the fiber misalignment in AS4/Polyetheretherketone (APC-2) coupons.

In this study the amount of lamina level waviness in AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy and S2 glass/3501-6 fiberglass/epoxy laminates was documented and its effect on the materials compression strength was quantified. Forty-eight ply $[0_2/90]_{8s}$ and ninety-six ply $[0_2/90]_{16s}$ laminates were investigated for lamina waviness. These and one-hundred and ninety-two ply $[0_2/90]_{32s}$ laminates were then analyzed and tested in compression. The materials were fabricated using manufacturers recommended cure cycles resulting in high quality laminates as determined by ultrasonic C-Scan, and average fiber volume fractions/void contents of 59.8% - /0.50% (AS4 panels) and 55.7%/ + 0.62% (S2 glass panels). Fiber volume fractions were determined by matrix digestion (ASTM D3171) or resin burn-off (ASTM D2734).

After measuring lamina waviness compression testing coupons were prepared and tested, and a compression failure analysis of the coupons was conducted to determine the effect of the initial lamina waviness and additional waviness caused by the application of a compressive load.

2. Lamina Level Waviness Measurements

The method used by Davis (1) to determine fiber undulation in boron reinforced composites was not applicable to the carbon and fiberglass reinforced ones studied in this investigation. Therefore a technique to easily quantify this undulation was developed.

In this technique the polished edges of $[0_2/90]$ laminates were inspected at 20X using an optical microscope with an x-z indexing table accurate to 0.0025 mm and fitted with cross hairs in the microscope eye pieces. The specimens were placed on the x-z indexing table at a slight angle to the x-axis, with the cross hairs intersecting one edge of the two midplane 90° plies and the adjacent 0° ply.

The x-axis was indexed 0.25 mm, and the z-axis was indexed to bring the same interface back to the cross hair intersection. This procedure was repeated at x-increments of 0.25 mm until a desired distance along the midplane has been characterized. The x-z coordinates of this single interface were recorded and adjusted for the angle the specimen made with the x-axis of the indexing table. This angle was determined from the recorded x-z data as

$$\theta_w = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n z_i}{n \times (0.01)} \right) \quad (1)$$

The laminate coordinate system and the interface measuring technique are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Laminate Coordinate System and Interface Measuring Technique

Three AS4/3501-6 and three S2 glass/3501-6 [0₂/90] laminates were inspected for lamina waviness. For each fiber type the transverse edge of a 48 ply and 96 ply specimen were measured, along with a longitudinal edge of a 96 ply specimen. The longitudinal direction waviness was measured along the specimen edge parallel to the 0° axis of the specimen, and the transverse direction waviness was measured along the edge parallel to the 90° axis of the specimen as shown in Figure 1. Midplane z-direction displacement versus distance along the midplane was plotted, and these curves were used to determine displacement amplitude and wavelength.

3. Method of Analysis

Budiansky (2) proposed a compression failure theory that included a fiber misalignment term as the geometric perturbation that creates a region of increased shear stress and triggers failure due to local instability. This failure theory was based on kink band formation as the mechanism of compression failure.

Budiansky extended Rosen's (9) elastic shear microbuckling solution for the ultimate compression strength $\sigma_m = G_{13}$ to include plasticity, assuming perfect plasticity in shear beyond $\gamma = \gamma_{13} = \tau_{13}/G_{13}$. The resulting expression is

$$\sigma_c = \left[\frac{\gamma_{13}}{\phi_o + \gamma_{13}} \right] \sigma_m = \left[\frac{\gamma_{13}}{\phi_o + \gamma_{13}} \right] G_{13} \quad (2)$$

where σ_c is the composites compression strength, τ_{13} is the composites ultimate transverse shear strength, γ_{13} is the composites ultimate transverse shear strain and ϕ_o is the initial misalignment angle.

The only source of fiber misalignment in this analysis is initial fiber waviness. In the coupons tested in compression for this program and to be discussed later, failures consistently occurred at the region where the specimen exited the fixture clamping blocks. In this region the outer plies of the laminates contain additional fiber misalignment (θ) due to the through-thickness expansion that occurs in the specimen unsupported gage section compared to the through-thickness expansion that occurs in the region within the fixture clamping blocks. Since the expansion within the gage section is the greater, then a fiber undulation occurs at the point where the specimen exits the fixture clamping blocks. This undulation is maximum at the outer surface of the specimens where compression failure was observed to initiate experimentally. This fiber misalignment is not initially present in the coupons, but develops with the

application of longitudinal compression load and increases with increasing load.

This misalignment was determined using a finite element analysis that included the effects of the restraint of the fixture clamping blocks on through-thickness expansion. The finite element analysis routine used was ABAQUS, and second order, orthotropic quadrilateral elements were employed. The displacement of the specimen outer surface as a function of uniaxial compression loading was determined with the finite element analysis, and this displacement information was used to determine the resultant fiber misalignment. The two sources of fiber misalignment were included in expression (2) as $\phi_0 = \theta_w + \theta$. A complete discussion of the analysis used to determine the load induced fiber misalignment is contained in Ref. (10).

Since Budiansky's compression failure theory and the finite element analysis were both linear elastic, linear elastic material properties were used in them. Significant nonlinear stress-strain response was reported when measuring the lamina properties for use in these analyses (Ref. 10), especially for the shear moduli and through-thickness Poisson's ratios. To account for these nonlinearities in the linear analysis conducted, secant tangent moduli taken from the origin to the stress and strain values at failure were used. These values are:

AS4/3501-6

$E_{11} = 107 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{12} = 0.352$	$G_{12} = 3.8 \text{ GPa}$
$E_{22} = 8.8 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{13} = 0.350$	$G_{13} = 3.8 \text{ GPa}$
$E_{33} = 8.8 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{23} = 0.649$	$G_{23} = 2.3 \text{ GPa}$

S2 glass/3501-6

$E_{11} = 48.6 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{12} = 0.311$	$G_{12} = 3.8 \text{ GPa}$
$E_{22} = 9.7 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{13} = 0.331$	$G_{13} = 3.8 \text{ GPa}$
$E_{33} = 9.7 \text{ GPa}$	$\nu_{23} = 0.690$	$G_{23} = 2.3 \text{ GPa}$

4. Compression Testing

A schematic diagram of the fixture used for the compression testing is shown in Figure 2. In a fixture of this type load is applied to the ends of the specimen and clamping blocks are used to provide stability and prevent end-brooming at the point of load introduction. Hardened steel plates were used as load bearing surfaces and inserted between both ends of the specimen and the test machine crosshead platens. The surfaces of these plates were ground flat and parallel within 0.025 mm. A lubricated, self aligning spherical seat was placed between

one end of the specimen and the load machine to assist in aligning the specimen axis and the loading axis.

The geometry of the compression test specimens was designed so that the width was 4 times the specimen thickness, the gage length was 5 times the specimen thickness, and the tab length was 5 times the specimen thickness (with a

Figure 2. Compression Test Fixture

minimum tab length of 63.5 mm). This geometry insured global stability of the specimen gage section without the use of additional side support. The nominal specimen thickness studied were the 6.4 mm (48 ply) and 12.7 mm (96 ply) specimens used for the waviness studies and 25.4 mm (192 ply) specimen.

Tabs were fabricated separately from the same material as each specimen, with a [0/90] orientation, and adhesively bonded to the test specimen panels after both the specimens and tabs were cured. After tabbing, individual specimens were machined to final tolerance by grinding the specimen ends, sides and tab surfaces parallel and perpendicular within 0.025 mm.

The specimens were instrumented with foil backed electrical resistance strain gages on both faces of the 48 ply specimens, and on all four surfaces of the thicker specimens. Complete details of the experimental portion of this program are discussed further in reference (10).

5. Results

Examples of the midplane lamina waviness data measured on the optical microscope are shown in Figure 3. Portions of curves such as these were used to pick off the amplitude and wavelength of a single whole or half-wavelength undulation. The lamina waviness was assumed to take the form of a sine function with its amplitude (a), wavelength (λ) and misalignment angle (θ_w) as defined in Figure 4.

The final results from the lamina level waviness study are listed in Table 1, and are shown graphically in Figure 5. The coefficients of variation in Table 1 are large, but only a few amplitude-to-wavelength ratios were averaged for each specimen (less than 6), and amplitudes and wavelengths were quite varied over the 50.8 or 101.6 mm characterized as seen in Figure 3. Included in Figure 5 are the results from Davis (1) for boron/epoxy, and the results from the carbon and S2 glass samples investigated here are comparable to his result. Figure 5 also shows that the lamina waviness is dependent on laminate stacking sequence since the amplitude-to-wavelength ratio for the transverse direction of the carbon laminates is twice that for the longitudinal direction.

Table 2 lists the final results of the analysis on fiber misalignment produced by the differential gage-section and fixture section expansion. The misalignment angles shown in this table correspond to those at the ultimate compression load determined experimentally for each laminate. The total fiber misalignment angle (ϕ_0) will then be used in the compression strength analysis.

To determine the ultimate compression strength for the two materials tested using Equation 2, their ultimate shear strength and ultimate shear strain at failure were needed. This information was determined from a ± 45 tension test of $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ specimens for each material. The tests were conducted and the data analyzed in accordance with ASTM D3518. This test methods yields τ_{12} and γ_{12} , which were assumed to be equivalent to τ_{13} and γ_{13} based on transverse isotropy. The choice of τ_{12} and γ_{12} from this test method is somewhat arbitrary, since continual elongation of the test specimens rather than distinct failure typically occurs. For this study shear failure was assumed to occur when the shear specimens could no longer carry any tensile load, and this failure occurred at approximately 75.9 MPa and 20,000 microstrain for both material systems. These numbers then yielded a secant shear modulus of 3.8 GPa as listed with the material properties above.

Longitudinal Waviness From a 96 Ply S2 glass/3501-6 Specimen

Figure 3. Plots of Midplane Lamina Waviness

Waviness Geometry Parameters

Figure 4. Waviness Geometry Parameters

Lamina Level Waviness Comparison

Figure 5. Lamina Level Waviness Results

Table 1. Waviness Induced Fiber Misalignment Data

	Average a, mm	Average λ , mm	Average a/λ	Average θ_w , °
AS4/3501-6 48 ply, Transverse	0.036 (35.7) ¹	7.57 (27.6)	0.0047 (12.7)	1.70 (12.9)
AS4/3501-6 96 ply Transverse	0.030 (57.4)	5.93 (41.7)	0.0054 (27.5)	1.94 (27.8)
AS4/3501-6 96 ply, Longitudinal	0.015 (42.1)	10.6 (63.9)	0.0018 (41.5)	0.66 (40.1)
S2/3501-6 48 ply, Transverse	0.010 (25.0)	4.12 (42.4)	0.0025 (7.6)	0.90 (7.8)
S2/3501-6 96 ply, Transverse	0.010 (50.0)	7.59 (51.1)	0.0015 (20.4)	0.53 (20.8)
S2/3501-6 96 ply, Longitudinal	0.015 (17.2)	6.49 (30.5)	0.0023 (18.4)	0.82 (18.3)

¹ coefficient of variation (%)

Table 2. Load Induced Fiber Misalignment Data

	$[0_2/90]_{8s}$	$[0_2/90]_{16s}$	$[0_2/90]_{32s}$
	AS4/3501-6		
Expansion θ , $^\circ$	0.789	0.998	1.18
Initial θ_w , $^\circ$	0.660	0.660	0.660
Total ϕ_0 , $^\circ$ (radians)	1.45 (0.0253)	1.66 (0.0289)	1.84 (0.0321)
	S2 glass/3501-6		
Expansion θ , $^\circ$	0.688	0.843	1.05
Initial θ_w , $^\circ$	0.820	0.820	0.820
Total ϕ_0 , $^\circ$ (radians)	1.51 (0.0263)	1.66 (0.0290)	1.87 (0.0326)

A comparison of the theoretical and experimental compression strength results are shown in Table 3. This comparison is made on the effective stress in the 0° plies of the $[0_2/90]$ laminate since Equation 2 is the the form for a unidirectional lamina. The effective 0° ply stress was determined from a laminate plate theory analysis of the $[0_2/90]$ laminates using the lamina input data previously described. The experimental results in Table 3 show that the compression strength of the $[0_2/90]$ laminates appears to decrease with increasing laminate thickness. Comparison of the experimental results with theoretical predictions indicates that this drop in strength can be attributed to the fiber misalignment that occurs from initial lamina waviness and load induced lamina waviness. Again, the load induced waviness results from fixture restraint where the specimen tabs terminate and the specimen gage section begins. When both sources of lamina waviness are included in the compression failure analysis the theoretical predictions fall within 16% of the experimental values with the exception of the $[0_2/90]_{32s}$ S2 glass laminates.

One further demonstration of the correlation between compression strength and fiber misalignment can be seen in Figure 6. In this figure experimentally measured compression strength is plotted against the total fiber misalignment angle (ϕ_0), that contains the experimentally determined initial fiber waviness (θ_w) and the theoretically determined load induced fiber waviness (θ). These results show a linear relationship between compression strength and lamina waviness, and support other theoretical studies that show the sensitivity of compression strength to fiber misalignment.

The important conclusion from the above results is that a direct relationship between theoretical sensitivity to fiber misalignment and experimentally determined compression strength is established. Most significantly this correlation is made at the region of failure initiation. The theoretical and experimental correlation could be improved with by conducting a full nonlinear stress analysis of the problem in place of the linear analysis performed here. In addition shear stress concentration effects in the area of failure initiation were not considered, and could possibly account for the 16 - 20% lower experimental values for compression strength.

Table 3. Comparison of Theoretical and Experimental Results

All Strength in MPa	Laminate Strength	0° Ply Stress at Failure	Theoretical Strength Eq. 2	Percentage Difference
AS4/3501-6				
[0 ₂ /90] _{8s}	1080	1570	1680	-6.6%
[0 ₂ /90] _{16s}	890	1300	1550	-16%
[0 ₂ /90] _{32s}	842	1230	1460	-16%
S2 glass/3501-6				
[0 ₂ /90] _{8s}	987	1370	1640	-16%
[0 ₂ /90] _{16s}	932	1290	1550	-17%
[0 ₂ /90] _{32s}	800	1110	1440	-23%

Figure 6. Compression Strength as a Function of Fiber Misalignment

6. Conclusions

The well established theoretical relationship between fiber misalignment due to lamina waviness and reduced compression strength has been shown experimentally in this paper. Lamina waviness resulting from standard autoclave manufacturing methods was quantified through an optical measurement technique. Lamina waviness due to applied compressive loading in the region of a shear stress concentration was quantified theoretically. The sum of these two effects was totalled and input into a kink-band compression failure analysis to demonstrate this relationship.

The effect of significant material nonlinearities that were observed experimentally were included in the linear elastic analyses used in this investigation through the use of reduced elastic material constants. These reduced properties were partially responsible for the good agreement between theoretical predictions and experimental results, indicating the need for using fully nonlinear analysis in compression failure analyses. Since the compression failure theory utilized is based on kink band failure triggered by local shear instability, and kink band failures were the predominant mode of failure in the compression experiments conducted, the development of nonlinear kink band failure theories is warranted.

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Biography

Gene Camponeschi is a Senior Project Engineer in the Materials Department of the David Taylor Research Center. He received his Ph. D. from the University of Delaware and specializes in the theoretical and experimental mechanics of composite materials. His most recent research programs have dealt with linear and nonlinear response of thick-section composites and the mechanics of 3D reinforced composite materials.

